

DYNAMIC MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF CELLULOSE NANOFIBER/POLYESTER RESIN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, lignocellulosic fibers such as cellulose fibers and nanofibers, have received much attention due to their high rigidity and low cost. Cellulose is an abundant natural polymer, with an estimated biomass production of 7.10^{10} t per year, and it is mainly used in softwood and hardwood paper industries. This study presents a recently developed method for processing cellulose residues by grinding them into cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) to be used in composite materials. Cellulose residues from hardwood (CNF-E - *Eucalyptus sp.*) and softwood (CNF-P - *Pinus sp.*) were ground in water (3 wt% per volume) in a Masuko MKCA 6-2 grinder at 2,500 rpm until gel was formed. Solvent exchange procedures using 96°G ethanol were performed and the gel suspension was dried in a supercritical dryer-using carbon dioxide as supercritical fluid. The obtained fibers were dispersed in a polyester resin in concentrations of 0.5, 1 and 2 wt%. The samples were prepared by resin casting and cured in situ for 24 h at 25°C. Two post-curing steps were performed: 6 h at 80°C and 2 h at 120°C. CNFs were evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and field emission gun scanning electron microscopy (FEG-SEM). Composites samples were evaluated by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). The size and the chemical composition of the fibers of CNFs were not significantly altered after supercritical drying. Storage modulus of the CNF-E 2% composite was slightly higher than the neat resin in the rubbery region. The tan delta peaks did not significantly shift at higher temperatures. Peak height was higher than the neat resin for all composites. Adhesion factor (A) was calculated and the lowest value was found for the CNF-E 0.5% composite, possibly indicating better adhesion at the fiber/matrix interface.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, great attention has been given to sustainable, environmental friendly materials for several applications. Composite materials derived from lignocellulosic fibers, such as cellulose and cellulose nanofibers, have turned into an area of intense scientific research due to their interesting properties such as high rigidity, low cost and renewable sources [1]. Worldwide cellulose biomass production is estimated at approximately $7.5 \cdot 10^{10}$ t per year, making it an abundant natural polymer mainly used in hardwood and softwood paper industries. In Brazil, the estimated hardwood (*Eucalyptus sp.*) and softwood (*Pinus sp.*) celluloses production in the first months of 2013 were $2,531.10^3$ t and 310.10^3 t, respectively [2]. As such, a great amount of residues is generated, and the waste must be properly

managed.

Cellulose is a natural polymer composed by two anhydroglucose rings bound together by β -1,4-glycosidic bonds. Its polymer chains are bound by hydrogen bonds and van der Waals forces forming structures called microfibrils [3]. These microfibrils usually have a highly ordered (crystalline) region and a disordered (amorphous) region. Cellulose fibrils have high aspect ratio and, due to their crystalline regions, they also have a high elastic modulus estimated in 25 GPa [4, 5].

There is a growing interest in processing cellulose into nanocellulose fibrils. One of the most common methods cited in the literature is the acid hydrolysis, which consists in freeing the nanocrystals of the amorphous regions of the cellulose fibrils by means of strong acid treatments. This process yields nanocrystalline cellulose (NCC) with a very low amount of amorphous components. It is, however, expensive and has a low yield [6]. A novel method of processing cellulose into nanocellulose has been proposed by Jonoobi et al (2012). It consists in passing never-dried or dried cellulose pulp water suspensions through a grinder in which two stones, by means of centrifuge forces, make it so that the cellulose passes through a very small opening, fibrillating the cellulose into a net of several cellulose nanofibers (CNF), with a length of dozens of micrometres and diameter within 100 nm. This is a relatively cost-efficient method of processing cellulose waste and transforming it into a highly valuable material [7].

One of the main challenges for composite production is the proper dispersion of nanocellulose in polymers. Since cellulose is a very polar structure and the majority of the polymers are essentially non polar, incompatibility ensues, leading to fiber agglomeration within the matrix [8]. This problem has led to a search for a proper method of drying cellulose nanofibrils. When drying nanocellulose through conventional methods such as oven drying, a phenomenon known as hornification occurs. Hornification is the irreversible agglomeration of fibers. In this phenomenon, the fibrils form a high number of hydrogen bonds with adjacent fibers. The result is a type of material that cannot be redispersed, and the nanoscale is lost [9]. Novel methods for drying cellulose have been investigated by Peng et al [10]. The authors studied the freeze drying, supercritical drying and spray drying of nanocellulose. Their results cited supercritical drying as the most efficient method to keep the nanoscale dimensions of the fibrils while also providing materials that can be redispersed.

This study aims to obtain thermoset polyester resin composites reinforced by nanocellulose fibers obtained by grinding dried waste materials of hardwood and softwood celluloses, and to investigate the effect of the nanocellulose fillers in the dynamic mechanical properties of the composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Cellulose residues from bleached hardwood (*Eucalyptus sp.*) and unbleached softwood (*Pinus sp.*) were obtained in dried form. Unsaturated orthophtalic polyester resin was donated by Elekeiroz. A content of 45% of styrene and a density of 1,100 kg/m³ were reported by the manufacturer. Methylketone peroxide (MEKP - Butanox LPT) was used as a cure promoter and dimethylaniline (DMA) was used as a catalyst.

2.2 Methods

Dried cellulose pulp residues of hardwood and softwood fibers were dispersed in 6 L of water (3 wt% per volume) and left in dispersion for 24 h prior to grinding. The suspensions were ground in a Masuko MKCA6-2 grinder at 2,500 rpm for approximately 4 hours, under a continuous feed provided by a recirculation pump system, until gel was formed. The obtained gels of nanofibers were solvent exchanged to 96 °G ethanol, in a proportion of 0:100, 25:75, 50:50, 75:25, 100:0 ethanol/water (% v/v), until complete exchange to ethanol was ensued.

Supercritical drying steps were performed in a Supercritical Fluid Technologies STF-150 SFE System supercritical extractor, using carbon dioxide (CO₂) as a supercritical fluid. The suspension was kept at 135 bar and 45 °C for 1 h in the static extraction period. A period of 45 min dynamic extraction was employed next, with CO₂ being constantly fed under controlled pressure above the supercritical point. These steps were repeated for 4 times before CO₂ feed valves were closed and a low decompression was carried overnight. Dried nanocellulose, in the form of aerogel, was obtained and ground in a small laboratory knife mill to separate the fibers. The nanocellulose fibers obtained from *Eucalyptus sp.* and from *Pinus sp.* were named CNF-E and CNF-P, respectively.

The obtained CNFs were dispersed in 100 g of polyester resin, under constant mechanical stirring at 1,500 rpm for 40 min. The concentrations of CNF used were 0.5, 1 and 2 wt%. After dispersion, the samples were placed under vacuum of -0.4 bar for 20 min prior to molding to remove air and bubbles from the samples. The composites were molded by resin casting in rubber silicone molds, where 1% MEKP was added to the resin and manually stirred for 1 min and 0.1% DMA was added right after. Curing was performed in situ for 24 h at room temperature (25 °C), followed by two post-curing steps: 6 h at 80 °C and 2 h at 120 °C. The obtained composites were termed CNF-P-X and CNF-E-X, where X means the weight percentage of nanocellulose *pinus or eucalyptus*, respectively.

The chemical composition of the cellulose samples before and after processing were evaluated by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) using the attenuated total reflectance technique (ATR), in a Nicolet equipment, model IS10, with a wavenumber range of 400 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹. Thermogravimetric analysis were carried to evaluate the thermal stability of the fibers before and after processing. The analysis were carried out in a Shimadzu equipment, model TA-60, in a temperature range of 30 °C to 800 °C, under a constant flux of 50 mL/min of N₂. Micrographs were obtained by field emission gun scanning electron microscopy (FEG-SEM) in a Tescan equipment model MIRA3. The viscoelastic properties of the composites were obtained by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) in a clamp single/dual cantilever, at a heating rate of 3 °C/min, with a temperature range from 30 °C to 190 °C, at a frequency of 1 Hz and a deformation amplitude of 0.1%. A TA Instruments equipment, model Q800 was used. Adhesion factor (A) was calculated according to Equation 1, where Φ_f is the volume fraction of reinforcement, $\tan\delta_c$ is the glass transition temperature (T_g) at the peak of tan delta curves of the composites and $\tan\delta_p$ is the T_g at the peak of tan delta curves of the neat polymer:

$$A = 1/(1 - \Phi_f) \cdot (\tan\delta_c / \tan\delta_p) - 1 \quad (1)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The density of the samples was calculated from the mass and volume of the aerogels. The density of CNF-P was 0.028 ± 0.007 g/cm³ and the density of CNF-E was 0.0319 ± 0.009 g/cm³.

The FTIR-ATR spectra of the raw *pinus* and *eucalyptus* cellulose, and the CNFs obtained from the fibers are displayed in Fig 1. The band at 3340 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the stretching vibration of the O-H bonds of the cellulose and the remaining water in the fibers. At 2900 cm⁻¹ there is the stretching of the C-H bond of the cellulose. The band at 1640 cm⁻¹ refers to the stretching vibration of the O-H bond of the absorbed water. The peak at 1430 cm⁻¹ is related to the bending of the symmetrical bond of the C-H₂ groups, and the peaks at 1370 cm⁻¹ and 1315 cm⁻¹ refer to the bending vibration of the C-H and C-O groups of the aromatic rings of the polysaccharides rings of the cellulose. The peak at 1030 cm⁻¹ is associated with the stretching vibration of the C-O and O-H bonds related to the polysaccharides. Finally, the peak at 895 cm⁻¹ is related to the β-glycosidic bonds amongst the monosaccharides of the cellulose [11-13].

Figure 1: FTIR-ATR spectra of cellulose and CNF samples.

The spectra of the two sources of cellulose sources do not significantly change. Moreover, the spectra of both CNF-P and CNF-E also remain unchanged when compared to the starting materials, and when compared to each other. It is possible that the subsequent washing, grinding and supercritical drying processes do not significantly alter the chemical composition of the surface of the fibers.

Thermogravimetric analysis of the studied cellulose and CNF samples are shown in Fig. 2a. Fig. 2b shows the first derivative of the weight loss obtained for all samples.

Figure 2: Thermogravimetric analysis of cellulose and CNF samples: (a) weight loss and (b) first derivative of weight loss.

Three main events of weight loss are noticed. The first one, occurring at around 65 °C and with a weight loss of 5.8 %, is related to the evaporation of the remaining water within the cellulose sample. The second weight loss event, with onset temperature on 325 °C, maximum weight loss rate occurring at 362 °C and a weight loss of 68.2 %, can be attributed to two main degradation mechanisms: the dehydration of the cellulose, caused by an endothermic process, followed by the thermal depolymerization of the cellulose [13]. The last event of weight loss from 374 °C onwards, with a weight loss of 23.1 %, is related to the thermal decomposition of the cellulose into D-glucopyranose monomers, which can be further decomposed in free radicals [14]. Table 1 shows all temperatures of maximum degradation rates and the percentage weight loss for all events, based on the data displayed

in Fig 2.b above.

Sample	First event		Second event		Third event
	T (°C)	Weight loss (wt%)	T (°C)	Weight loss (wt%)	Residual mass (wt%)
<i>Pinus sp.</i>	65	5.8	362	68.2	23.1
<i>Eucalyptus sp.</i>	53	5.6	362	72.5	18.5
CNF-P	60	5.8	355	68.0	15.4
CNF-E	53	6.2	355	77.3	9.9

Table 1: Weight loss events and maximum degradation temperatures for all cellulose and CNF samples.

The weight loss in the second event for CNF-P was not significantly altered when compared with its source material. On the other hand, CNF-E had higher weight loss percentage when compared to eucalyptus fibers. This is possibly due to the higher surface area obtained by the supercritical drying method, resulting in a network of separated fibrils. In the source material, the fibrils are compact, which limits the effective surface area, and thus lower weight loss. The same phenomenon is applicable to the residual mass values, which are lower in both CNF-P and CNF-E samples. When comparing the temperatures of maximum degradation rate on the second event of weight loss, it was observed that both CNF-P and CNF-E are less thermally stable. This is due to the formation of a charcoal film on the surface of the fibers in the source material, which prevents the internal fibrils from suffering degradation. Again, the more the fibril network was separated in the CNF samples, the more the degradation was facilitated, thus lowering the thermal stability [10]. Since polyester resin has reached a maximum temperature of 170 °C during the curing, the maximum degradation temperatures are not a problem for the composite casting process.

Fig. 3 shows FEG-SEM micrographs for CNF-P and CNF-E samples. It can be noted that the morphology of the nanofibers consists of a network of fibrils with several micrometers in length and approximately 70-90 nm in diameter, staying within the nanometric range. No significant changes in the morphology of the fibers can be observed. For CNF-P, however, it is noted that the fibrils are more compact in some areas, whereas CNF-E nanofibers are slightly less agglomerated. Moreover, it can be seen that some dirt on the CNF-P surface was not completely removed in the micronizing and supercritical drying processes. Still, it was possible to dry cellulose nanofibrils maintaining their nanometric scale.

Figure 3: FEG-SEM micrographs of (a) CNF-P and (b) CNF-E.

3.3 Dynamic Mechanical Analyses of the Composites

Dynamic mechanical analysis of CNF-P and CNF-E were performed. Fig 4a and Fig. 4b show the storage modulus (E') for CNF-P and CNF-E composites, respectively.

Figure 4: Storage modulus of (a) CNF-P and (b) CNF-E composites.

No significant changes were observed for the storage modulus (E') in the glassy region for all composites. In the rubbery region, however, a slightly different behavior was noted. For the CNF-P-0.5% composite the E' modulus values were lower than those of the neat polymer. When the percentage of filler is increased, the values are close to those of the polyester resin. In the CNF-E composites, a trend is observed: as more filler was added to the matrix, the E' modulus in the rubbery kept increasing, with CNF-E-2% having slightly higher values than the neat resin.

In polymers, the addition of reinforcements in the matrix can lead to the restriction of the free movement of the polymer chains, *i. e.*, it can be related to the rigidity of the polymer [15, 16]. In this case, agglomeration of the fibers in the polymer might have led to the poor dynamic-mechanical performance in the rubbery region for the CNF-P-2% composite in contrast with CNF-E composites. According to Tonoli et al [17], *eucalyptus* fibers are generally smaller in length than *pinus* fibers. This provides a higher specific area and can lead to better dispersion in the matrix. *Pinus* fibers, on the

other hand, are longer, and can entangle easily [17]. In this case, the best behavior of CNF-E-2% composites can be justified by the slight better dispersion of *eucalyptus* fibers in the polyester resin when compared to *pinus* fibers.

Fig. 5 shows the damping (tan delta) of CNF-P (Fig. 5a) and CNF-E (Fig. 5b) composites.

Figure 5: Tan delta curves of (a) CNF-P and (b) CNF-E composites.

The incorporation of a reinforcement to the matrix leads to the restriction of the free movement of the polymer molecules, thus yielding a lower peak height for composites when compared to the neat polymer. At high filler concentration (CNF = 1 or 2%) there is a higher restriction of the polymer matrix molecules when compared to those observed in lower concentrations (CNF < 0.5%). However, the peak heights of all composites are higher than that of the polyester resin. This could possibly be caused by the bad dispersion of the CNFs in the neat resin. Visakh et al [18] found similar results for natural rubber reinforced with cellulose nanowhiskers in a concentration of 2.5%. In this case, the authors did not find a plausible explanation for this behavior.

Table 2 shows the glass transition temperature (T_g) and the adhesion factor (A) calculated for CNF-P and CNF-E composites.

Reinforcement (wt%)	T_g (°C)		Adhesion Factor (A)	
	CNF-P	CNF-E	CNF-P	CNF-E
0.5 %	124.1	123.3	0.2233	0.1840
1 %	122.1	123.6	0.5379	0.4578
2 %	122.4	123.9	2.4688	1.6894

*Neat polyester resin: 123.5 °C.

Table 2: Glass transition temperatures (T_g) and adhesion factor (A) of CNF-P and CNF-E composites.

A slight shift to a higher T_g was observed for the CNF-P-0.5% composite. For the other CNF-P composites, T_g values were lower than that found for the neat polymer. The T_g of all CNF-E composites was very similar to that of the polyester resin. The displacement of the T_g peak to higher temperatures is related to the reduction of the molecular mobility of the polymer chains, which can indicate better fiber/matrix adhesion [15]. The adhesion at the interface can be calculated by the adhesion factor A. This factor relates the relative damping of the composite and the neat polymer, and the volume fraction of reinforcement used. As a general rule, lower values indicate better adhesion. The lowest values were found for the CNF-E composites, being the CNF-E-0.5% the composite with

the lowest adhesion factor. In this work, however, the values increased as the CNFs were added. For both CNF-P-2% and CNF-E-2% composites values higher than 1 were found. This is an anomalous behavior not yet reported by the literature. Ornaghi et al [15] found the same results as the present study, as follows: the values of A increased as the filler was added. Correa et al [19] used this correlation to evaluate the effect of a coupling agent on the dynamic-mechanical properties of polypropylene/wood composites. The authors reported that this correlation may fail due to two main reasons: the model does not consider the intrinsic properties of the reinforcement. It also fails to predict the effects of a possible interphase formation between the polymer and the fibers, which directly impacts the adhesion [15, 19]. As such, it can be concluded that even though the CNF-E-0.5% composite had the lowest value for A, the results of the adhesion factor are inconclusive. One of the reasons for that could be due to bad dispersion of the CNFs in the polyester resin – a result supported by the higher tan delta peak heights observed in Fig. 5.

4 CONCLUSION

Cellulose nanofibers from dried residues were successfully obtained through mechanical processing in water followed by supercritical drying. The diameter of the fibers ranged from approximately 70 to 90 nm, which is well within the nanometric range. The chemical composition of CNF-P and CNF-E does not differ greatly, and it is not altered by the grinding or drying processes. Thermal stability of CNFs was lower than that of the raw material. Storage modulus was only changed for CNF-E-2% composites, indicating higher rigidity. Glass transition temperature was not significantly changed in the composites. Tan delta peaks indicated that good dispersion of the CNFs in the neat resin was not successfully achieved, which is further supported by the adhesion factor values found in this study.

Based on storage modulus results, *eucalyptus* fibers are better suited for composite applications, due to their shorter length and easier dispersion, in contrast to *pinus* fibers, which can entangle and might not be dispersed as easily.

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